

DEVELOPMENT OF SERVICE IN ECOLOGICAL AND RELIGIOUS TOURISM OBJECTS AS EXAMPLE, CHOR-CHINAR ECOLOGICAL-RELIGIOUS COMPLEX, URGUT DISTRICT IN SAMARKAND REGION.

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ABSTRACT

This master's thesis explores the impact of service quality on tourist satisfaction and loyalty within the context of Chor-chinor religious and ecological site. The study addresses the lack of existing services in religious and environmental facilities, emphasizing the importance of improving quality to attract and retain tourists. Through quantitative research and oral interviews, the study highlights the significance of enhancing services such as transport, dining, and auxiliary facilities to meet tourists' expectations. The research reveals that the marketing efforts to attract tourists to the area are inadequate, and basic services need improvement. Additionally, the e-service system needs to be upgraded to meet modern standards. The findings suggest that service quality elements have a significant influence on tourist satisfaction and loyalty, with a positive relationship between visitor pleasure and loyalty. The study concludes that tourists are dissatisfied with essential services, indicating the need for enhancement in order to meet the evolving needs and expectations of tourists. This research contributes to the development of ecological and religious pilgrimage tourism, highlighting the economic benefits and improvement in the standard of living for the local population. By identifying shortcomings and offering suggestions for improvement, this study aims to enhance the overall tourism experience at Chor-chinor shrine.

Keywords: satisfaction, ecological tourism, religious tourism, Chor-chinor shrine, service.

INTRODUCTION

The Central Asian region is known for its rich history and diverse natural beauty, with Uzbekistan standing out for its ancient past and unique landscapes. Despite its potential, there are still many undiscovered gems in this region that have yet to be fully explored. In light of this, the government has taken steps to promote the rapid development of tourism, especially focusing on religious

shrines located in ecologically significant areas. One of the key strategies for promoting sustainable tourism in the region is through ecotourism, which aims to protect the environment, preserve nature, and promote responsible travel practices. Religious tourism also plays a significant role in attracting visitors, with religious sites attracting not only followers of a specific faith but also those interested in exploring the historical and cultural significance of these locations. Ecotourism is defined as "responsible travel to natural areas that protects the environment, observes its natural conditions, ensures the well-being of local residents, and includes interpretation and education." This type of tourism not only benefits the environment but also educates visitors and tourism workers about environmental issues and cultural heritage. Religious tourism, on the other hand, is a thriving segment of the tourism market, attracting visitors from various backgrounds to explore the historical and cultural significance of religious sites.

One such location that combines both ecotourism and religious tourism is the Chor Chiyor Sufi madrasa in Uzbekistan. With its environmentally pure environment and a 12-century-old maple grove, it is a significant spiritual and cultural site that attracts pilgrims and visitors alike. By improving the quality of services provided at such sites and offering a range of additional amenities, it is possible to enhance the overall tourism experience and contribute to the local economy.

The main purpose of this research is to develop a predictive model of customer satisfaction with the services offered at religious and ecological tourism sites using machine learning capabilities. By identifying the most influential attributes of such sites, it will be possible to enhance the overall visitor experience and improve the quality of services provided. The specific objectives of the study include analyzing the theoretical and practical aspects of tourism object service, determining the most significant components of the Relational Model of Service Quality in religious and ecological tourist destinations, and predicting customer satisfaction with these sites.

By analyzing the quality of services provided at religious and ecological tourism destinations, identifying key attributes that influence visitor satisfaction, and developing predictive models, this research aims to contribute to the improvement of tourism services in the region. By enhancing the visitor experience and promoting sustainable tourism practices, it is possible to unlock the full potential of religious and ecological tourism sites in Uzbekistan and beyond.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Tourism is a dynamic economic sector that shapes contemporary civilization development. Structural and conjunctural factors influence tourist growth, presenting tourism as a means of fostering mutual understanding and cultural exchange (Saidjalolov Saidafzal, 2020). The multifaceted nature of tourism is driven by human desires for entertainment, information, education, and personal growth within a post-industrial society (OA Bunakov, NA Zaitseva, AA Larionova, 2018).

Development of services in religious and ecological areas

Various studies highlight the importance of sustainable practices in enhancing tourism and preserving natural resources. Ecotourism, with a focus on conservation and community engagement, seeks to strike a balance between tourism and environmental protection (Liutikas, Darius, 2015). Religious tourism, on the other hand, offers unique spiritual experiences aimed at cultural and personal enrichment (K Shinde, Religions, 2021).

The Chor-Chinor shrine

The Chor-Chinor shrine, located in Urgut, Uzbekistan, is a sacred and historical site that holds significant cultural and spiritual importance. The name “Chor-Chinor” translates from Persian as “four plane trees,” which are a defining feature of the shrine’s landscape. The sanctuary is situated approximately 3 kilometers from Urgut’s town and is surrounded by a stunning natural setting that adds to its tranquility and mystique.

The grove at the Chor-Chinor shrine is adorned with over fifty ancient plane trees, some of which are estimated to be over a thousand years old. These old plane trees serve as a symbol of the region’s rich cultural heritage and spiritual significance (Qulmatov Sh, Berdimurodov A, 2017). The massive, hollow centers of these trees are believed to have been used as classrooms, adding to the historical aura of the shrine.

Within the Chor-Chinor shrine complex, visitors can find tall adobe buildings, winding streets, and vibrant ethnic groups reminiscent of Bukhara’s former neighborhoods. The layout of the streets and homes, arranged on an incline and spread out along both banks of the Urgutsaya mountain river, provides a unique and picturesque ambiance to the sanctuary. The tranquil environment and natural beauty of the grove make it a peaceful retreat for both pilgrims and tourists seeking a quiet and spiritual experience.

An index attached to each tree in the grove indicates its estimated age, with some trees dating back over eleven centuries. The trees and the surrounding

landscape create a sacred atmosphere that draws visitors seeking spiritual solace and cultural enrichment. The presence of mosques, graves, and a holy spring further adds to the shrine's spiritual significance, making it a site of pilgrimage and religious importance for many individuals (Soliyev A.S., Tashtayeva S.K., 2018).

In conclusion, the Chor-Chinor shrine stands as a testament to Uzbekistan's rich history and cultural heritage. Its ancient plane trees, historic buildings, and tranquil surroundings make it a unique and spiritually significant destination for pilgrims and visitors alike. The shrine's peaceful ambiance and natural beauty continue to attract those seeking a meaningful and serene experience in the heart of Uzbekistan's cultural landscape.

Summary

In conclusion, tourism plays a vital role in economic, cultural, and environmental spheres, influencing global relationships and cultural exchanges. Sustainable tourism practices, as evident in ecotourism and religious tourism, are crucial for preserving natural and cultural heritage while promoting responsible travel behavior (Rainisto, S.K., 2003). The development of services in religious and ecological areas, exemplified by the case of Chor-Chinor shrine, offers opportunities for enhancing visitor experiences and promoting cultural understanding (Dmitry M. Astanin, 2019). By integrating these principles into tourism practices, stakeholders can work collaboratively to ensure sustainable tourism development and environmental conservation, shaping the future of the tourism industry (Triantafillidou, B., and Koritos, A., 2010).

METHODOLOGY

Quantitative Research

Quantitative research is employed in this study to objectively describe the perceptions of ecotourists regarding service quality at the Chor-Chinor shrine for ecological and religious tourism. This form of research uses standardized tools and statistical analysis to derive insights from predetermined categories and expectations (Sakae, Y.; Kato, T., 2016). Data is collected through structured questionnaires, surveys, and interviews to capture the frequency and extent of certain facts and opinions within the target population. The approach allows for statistical and mathematical techniques to be utilized in analyzing data to draw meaningful conclusions about the service quality experiences of visitors to the shrine (Goldkuhl, G., 2012).

Research Design

The research design focuses on quantitative methods, primarily experiments and surveys to assess visitors' perceptions of service quality at the Chor-Chinor shrine. The study utilizes deductive reasoning and various analysis techniques to provide descriptive data and establish statistical relationships through modeling (Saunders et al., 2009). By applying quantitative research principles, the study aims to quantitatively measure the level of service quality development at the Chor-Chinor site and identify any variation in perceptions among different regions.

Data Analysis

Data analysis in quantitative research involves the entry of raw data into programs such as Microsoft Excel or IBM SPSS for evaluation of survey results. While basic descriptive statistics are available in some tools, advanced statistical tests can be conducted using programs like SPSS to analyze quantitative data more comprehensively. Analysis methods will provide insights into the main challenges faced by visitors at the Chor-Chinor shrine and identify shortcomings in the services provided at the site (Goldkuhl, G., 2012).

Research Questions

The research aims to address the following questions to assess the quality of service provision at the Chor-Chinor shrine:

1. What are the main inconveniences facing visitors to the Chor-Chinor shrine?
2. What are the shortcomings of the main and additional services provided at the Chor-Chinor shrine?
3. What is the economic significance of the Chor-Chinor shrine in the region?

Interview Methodology

Interviews play a crucial role in gathering comprehensive insights and reporting specific opinions of informants in research studies. The structured interview process involves methodologies that emphasize research procedures leading to quantitative analyses, such as questionnaires, interviews, and data analysis (Gabble, G. G., 1994). The interview method will facilitate a deeper exploration of visitors' perceptions and experiences at the shrine, allowing for a detailed examination of service quality and potential areas for improvement.

Data Collection Methods

Data collection methods will play a pivotal role in the success and cost-effectiveness of the research project. Various data collection techniques will be utilized, ranging from paper forms to portable electronic devices, to ensure the collection of diverse perspectives from visitors at the Chor-Chinor shrine. The recruitment of participants will be conducted transparently to ensure that

individuals who can provide valuable insights into the research questions are included (Keith Crump, 2018).

Through a combination of quantitative research, interviews, and advanced data analysis techniques, this study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of visitors' perceptions and assess the service quality at the Chor-Chinor shrine, offering valuable insights for further development and improvement in the region.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

		Historical Significance			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Indifferent	1	1,8	1,8	1,8
	Crucial	15	27,3	27,3	29,1
	Extremely Crucial	39	70,9	70,9	100,0
	Total	55	100,0	100,0	

		Quality of Services (food)			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Poor	25	45,5	45,5	45,5
	Average	7	12,7	12,7	58,2
	Good	13	23,6	23,6	81,8
	Excellent	10	18,2	18,2	100,0
	Total	55	100,0	100,0	

		Price of Goods and Services			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1. Very Low	8	14,5	14,5	14,5
	2. Low	13	23,6	23,6	38,2
	3. Indifferent	13	23,6	23,6	61,8
	4. High	19	34,5	34,5	96,4
	5. Very High	2	3,6	3,6	100,0
	Total	55	100,0	100,0	

Ecological Significance

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not Important	2	3,6	3,6	3,6
	Indifferent	7	12,7	12,7	16,4
	Crucial	29	52,7	52,7	69,1
	Extremely Crucial	17	30,9	30,9	100,0
	Total	55	100,0	100,0	

Cuisine and Dining

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	2. Disappointed	22	40,0	40,0	40,0
	3. Indifferent	14	25,5	25,5	65,5
	4. Satisfied	14	25,5	25,5	90,9
	5. Very Satisfied	5	9,1	9,1	100,0
	Total	55	100,0	100,0	

Quality of Services (Transport)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Poor	22	40,0	40,0	40,0
	Average	15	27,3	27,3	67,3
	Good	15	27,3	27,3	94,5
	Excellent	3	5,5	5,5	100,0
	Total	55	100,0	100,0	

		Would Like to re-visit and			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	no	16	29,1	29,1	29,1
	yes	39	70,9	70,9	100,0
	Total	55	100,0	100,0	
		Recommendation			
Valid	0	1	1,8	1,8	1,8
	Yes	54	98,2	98,2	100,0
	Total	55	100,0	100,0	

The analysis of the questionnaire data collected from tourists visiting the Chor-chinar shrine offers valuable insights into the perceptions and experiences of visitors. The historical significance of the shrine emerged as a key aspect, with approximately 70% of respondents considering it extremely crucial. This highlights the importance of the shrine in the eyes of visitors, showcasing its rich cultural heritage and historical value. The ecological significance of the shrine was also rated positively, with over 83% of participants considering it crucial or extremely crucial. This indicates the environmental importance of the site and its role in promoting sustainability and conservation efforts.

However, when it comes to the quality of services, certain areas showed room for improvement. The transport services at the shrine were perceived as poor by 40% of visitors, suggesting issues with transportation infrastructure and efficiency. Similarly, food services were rated as poor by 45.5% of tourists, indicating dissatisfaction with the dining options available at the shrine. These findings underline the need to enhance transportation and dining services to meet visitor expectations and improve overall visitor satisfaction.

In terms of cuisine and dining experiences, 40% of participants expressed disappointment, while 25.5% were indifferent. This suggests that improvements in the quality and variety of food offerings could enhance the overall visitor experience. Additionally, the price of goods and services was perceived as high by 38.1% of respondents, indicating a potential need for adjustments in pricing to align with visitor expectations and enhance affordability.

Despite these challenges, the data revealed a positive inclination towards re-visiting the Chor-chinar shrine, with 70.9% of participants expressing a desire to return. This indicates a strong interest in revisiting the shrine and exploring its offerings further. Furthermore, an overwhelming 98.2% of respondents mentioned that they would recommend the shrine to others, highlighting the positive aspects of their experience and underscoring the potential for word-of-mouth promotion and future visitations.

In conclusion, the survey results suggest that visitor satisfaction plays a crucial role in influencing their intention to return to the shrine. Addressing key areas such as transportation, food services, and pricing could enhance the overall tourism experience and further attract visitors to the Chor-chinar shrine. By focusing on improving service quality, the shrine has the opportunity to elevate visitor satisfaction, foster repeat visits, and increase positive recommendations, ultimately contributing to the site’s long-term success and sustainability in the tourism industry.

		How have you heard			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1. Social Media	8	14,5	14,5	14,5
	2. Friends and relatives	15	27,3	27,3	61,8
	3. Travel agency	8	14,5	14,5	34,5
	4. Journal, Magazines, TV, Radio	3	5,5	5,5	20,0
	5. other	21	38,2	38,2	100,0
	Total	55	100,0	100,0	

		The proposes for improvement			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	development of restaurant quality	4	7,3	7,3	7,3
	everthing is good	1	1,8	1,8	9,1
	Everthings suits	1	1,8	1,8	10,9
	historical places turned into business field	1	1,8	1,8	12,7
	household service (toilet)	3	5,5	5,5	18,2
	internet connections	3	5,5	5,5	23,6
	no information board	4	7,3	7,3	30,9
	policy services	1	1,8	1,8	32,7
	Quality of public transport	1	1,8	1,8	34,5
	Quality of sevice	5	9,1	9,1	43,6
	reduction in price for tourists	2	3,6	3,6	47,3
	replace old tourist transport	2	3,6	3,6	50,9
	the number of kitchens is small	6	10,9	10,9	61,8
	there are places unorganised for tourists	1	1,8	1,8	63,6
	To develop a destination marketing	2	3,6	3,6	67,3
	To improve crosswalks	2	3,6	3,6	70,9
	To improve internet	1	1,8	1,8	72,7
	To improve marketing	1	1,8	1,8	74,5
	To invest non-cash payment with visacard	1	1,8	1,8	76,4
	To make more detailed explanations of items in another language	1	1,8	1,8	78,2
	To make translation counters in public transportation	2	3,6	3,6	81,8
	Local comunity	1	1,8	1,8	83,6
	To reduce prices for tourists	1	1,8	1,8	85,5
	too less shops	1	1,8	1,8	87,3
	Other service	3	5,5	5,5	92,7
	transportation	3	5,5	5,5	98,2
	very few places for entertainment	1	1,8	1,8	100,0
	Total	55	100,0	100,0	

The data analysis from the questionnaire responses provides valuable insight into how visitors learned about the Chor-chinar shrine and areas for improvement based on their experiences. It was found that social media and word-of-mouth through friends and relatives are significant channels through which visitors became aware of the shrine. This highlights the importance of enhancing marketing efforts through social media and networks to increase visitor awareness and attract more tourists to the site.

Recommendations for improvement were also provided by visitors, with a focus on developing restaurant quality, improving household services such as

restroom facilities, enhancing internet connections, and addressing informational gaps through information boards. Suggestions were also made to enhance the quality of public transport, reduce prices for tourists, and upgrade old tourist transportation to improve the overall visitor experience. Additionally, recommendations were made to invest in destination marketing, improve services, and provide non-cash payment options to cater to a wider range of visitors.

The data indicates that visitors have identified various areas where enhancements can be made to enhance the overall visitor experience at the Chor-chinar shrine. The proposed improvements reflect the importance of addressing service quality, pricing, transportation, and information dissemination to meet visitor expectations and attract more tourists to the shrine. By implementing these recommendations, the shrine has the potential to become a more appealing destination, drawing a larger number of visitors and contributing to the overall development of tourism in the Urgut region.

The analysis of visitor feedback underscores the significance of addressing existing deficiencies and capitalizing on the opportunities offered by the Chor-chinar shrine. By prioritizing the development of services, marketing efforts, and infrastructure improvements, the shrine can enhance its appeal as a tourist destination and provide visitors with a more enriching and satisfying experience. As the region continues to evolve as a hub for ecological and religious tourism, careful attention to visitor feedback and continual improvement initiatives will be crucial in unlocking the shrine's full potential as a prominent tourism destination.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study conducted on visitors at the Chor-chinar shrine has provided valuable insights into the tourism experience and areas for improvement. The potential of the Chor-Chinor shrine as a tourist destination is on the rise, presenting opportunities for economic development and job creation in the local community. As the region seeks to capitalize on its natural and cultural heritage through religious and ecotourism, enhancing services and infrastructure at the Chor-Chinor shrine is crucial for attracting visitors and preserving the environment.

Future research should focus on modifying tourist service quality, enhancing visitor satisfaction, exploring return intentions, and expanding the scope of tourism services at the Chor-chinar shrine. Consideration should also be given to promoting modern farming techniques and incorporating the shrine into tour

packages to increase its visibility and attract a wider audience. By leveraging the shrine's unique natural beauty and historical significance, the region can enhance its appeal as a tourism destination while promoting sustainable tourism practices.

Recommendations:

To support the development and promotion of the Chor-chinar shrine, several key recommendations are outlined:

1. Inclusion in Travel Agency Offerings: Add the Chor-chinar shrine to the list of services offered by travel agencies to increase visitor awareness and attract more tourists.
2. Marketing Strategies: Implement marketing campaigns to promote the shrine and increase its visibility through various advertising channels.
3. Social Media Engagement: Extend the reach of the shrine by establishing a strong presence on social media platforms to engage with a wide audience and attract potential visitors.

By implementing these recommendations, the Chor-chinar shrine can enhance its position as a sought-after tourist destination, contribute to economic growth in the region, and offer visitors a memorable and enriching tourism experience. Continued research, development, and strategic planning will be essential in realizing the full potential of the Chor-Chinor shrine as a prominent cultural and ecological tourism site.

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